

Supporting information for Table 1

1 Unlimited population growth

1.1 Population growth rate

(1) Methods

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{N_{t+5}}{N_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}}$$

Using the population data in Fig.1 (in main text) and above formula, the annual growth rate λ of the native Crested Ibis population is calculated at 5-year intervals, where N_t represents the population size at year t . A λ value approaching 1 indicates a stable population.

(2) Results

From 1981 to 2025, the annual growth rate of the population showed a fluctuating trend (Fig. S1). Over the most recent five-year period (2021–2025), the average annual growth rate approached 1 ($\lambda = 1.01$), indicating that the population exhibits a dynamic equilibrium mechanism and does not display unlimited growth.

Fig. S1 Changes in the annualized growth rate of the wild Crested Ibis population (1981-2025)

Note : t0(1981-1985), t1(1985-1989), t2(1989-1993), t3(1993-1997), t4(1997-2001), t5(2001-2005), t6(2005-2009), t7(2009-2013), t8(2013-2017), t9(2017-2021), t10(2021-2025)

1.2 Prediction of potentially suitable habitat

(1) Methods (For more details, see Huang et al., 2021)

Species distribution data: We mainly used the distribution sites of the wild Crested Ibis population

from 1990 to 2010. This period represents a critical stage in the gradual recovery of the Crested Ibis from a small population, and the habitat characteristics (i.e., the environmental niche) on which the population relied during this phase are highly indicative of successful population development. To reduce the influence of spatial autocorrelation, the data were further screened so that only one point was retained per grid cell. Finally, 133 nesting sites, 100 foraging sites, and 76 roosting sites were obtained and used in the analyses, all of which covered the actual distribution range of the wild Crested Ibis.

Environmental variables: We selected 19 bioclimatic variables closely related to the physiology and distribution of vertebrates, downloaded from the WorldClim database v.1.4.19 (<https://www.worldclim.org/>) at a resolution of 30 arc-seconds (~1 km). Topographic factors generally include elevation, slope, aspect, and topographic complexity. At large spatial scales, the information conveyed by slope and aspect often overlaps with that reflected by elevation and climate. Therefore, we chose elevation and topographic complexity as the two topographic factors. Elevation data were derived from a 90 m resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) downloaded from the Geospatial Data Cloud (<http://www.gscloud.cn/home>). We selected two land-cover variables most relevant to the Crested Ibis: paddy field and forestland. Paddy fields are a critically important foraging wetland type for many birds, especially the Crested Ibis. Moreover, the Crested Ibis requires tall trees for nesting, roosting, and perching, making forestland a fundamental habitat requirement. Land cover data were obtained from the 300 m resolution global land-cover data of from the European Space Agency GlobCover Portal (http://due.esrin.esa.int/page_globcover.php), from which land-cover types related to paddy fields and forestland were extracted and aggregated separately.

Prior to model analysis, we performed a collinearity test on all variables using Pearson correlation analysis. Variables with $|r| < 0.7$ were retained. Finally, eight variables (elevation, topographic complexity, paddy field, forestland, annual mean temperature, maximum temperature of the warmest month, mean temperature of the warmest season, and mean temperature of the coldest season) were selected for model analysis.

Analytical methods: Predictions were made using five representative species distribution models including MaxEnt. For each model, 80% of the original data were used as training data and 20% as validation data, and the procedure was repeated 10 times to obtain average results, ensuring that predictions were independent of the training data. Model accuracy was evaluated using the area under the curve (AUC) and the true skill statistic (TSS), and the model with the best accuracy was selected. The prediction results were classified into suitable and unsuitable areas using a threshold. The raw predictions were continuous raster data with suitability index values ranging from 0 to 1,000; therefore, they were normalized to a 0–1 range, and thresholds of 0.4 and 0.6 were used to divide the normalized continuous distribution map into moderately suitable and highly suitable areas.

(2) Results

Under the current climate scenario, the potential suitable habitat for the Crested Ibis in China is

58,634.75 km². Among this, the highly suitable area ($0.6 \leq \text{suitability index} \leq 1$) is 37,660 km², and the moderately suitable area ($0.4 \leq \text{suitability index} < 0.6$) is 20,974.75 km².

Huang Y. Spatio-temporal habitat selection of wild Crested Ibis (*Nipponia nippon*) and modeling of reintroduction sites. PhD thesis, Beijing Forestry University;2021.

2 Excessive population density

(1) Methods

In autumn and winter, Crested Ibises roost communally, resulting in relatively concentrated distributions. During the breeding season, however, they nest in a dispersed manner. Thanks to continuous conservation monitoring and active reporting by local residents, we were able to reliably and comprehensively obtain the locations of breeding nests for the current year. Therefore, the breeding season is an ideal period for surveying the distribution range and density of the Crested Ibis population. Based on nest survey data from the native population and the Tongchuan reintroduced population (one of three reintroduced populations in China that have initially established sustainability, with >100 individuals) in 2025, we used the kernel density estimation (KDE) function in the R package “adehabitatHR” to estimate total distribution area (95% KDE) and core distribution area (50% KDE).

Here, we focused on the higher-density core distribution area. Nest density was calculated as the number of nests in the core distribution area divided by the core area. This value was compared with that reported by Wang et al. (2020). If higher than the 2019 value, it indicates that population density continued to increase and had not yet reached an over-dense state; if roughly equal to or lower than the 2019 value, it suggests that the Crested Ibis population may reach a relatively high density between 2019 and 2025, experienced density-dependent effects, and breeding density no longer increased or even decreased.

(2) Results

In 2025, the total nest distribution area of the native Crested Ibis population was 3,111.18 km². The core distribution area was 470.29 km², with a breeding density of 1.29 nests/km². The 2019 density was 0.73 nests/km² (Wang et al., 2020). For the Tongchuan reintroduced population, the core nest distribution area was 300.87 km² in 2025, but contained only 22 nests, yielding a breeding density of 0.1 nests/km², far lower than that of the native population. Therefore, for both the native and reintroduced populations, there is no evidence of excessive density.

Wang C, Zhang Y, Zeng J, et al. Reproductive status and population size of wild Crested Ibis (*Nipponia nippon*) in China. *Scientia Silvae Sinicae*, 2020; 56(11): 143–150.

For the dispersal status of the native Crested Ibis population, see Ye et al. (2023).

Ye Y, Santoro S, Song Z, Hu C, Zhang Z, Qing B, et al. Dispersal patterns of the endangered Crested Ibis suggest high breeding densities drive natal dispersal. *Ornithol Appl.* 2023;125(1): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ornithapp/duac042>

3 Opportunity costs and ecosystem costs

We supplement the methodological details regarding the bird diversity survey. Although a comprehensive survey conducted in 2025 recorded 330 bird species within the reserve, representing a notable increase from the 201 species reported for the Crested Ibis activity area between 1999 and 2002. However, given that the earlier surveys lacked comparable survey intensity and methodology, in the manuscript we did not directly emphasize the overall increase in total bird species; instead, we focused on the 15 newly recorded waterbird species. Since 2020, workers have conducted annual wintering waterbird surveys in the reserve with identical timing, spatial extent, and sampling intensity. By the end of 2025, new waterbird species were recorded each year. The detailed methods and results are as follows:

(1) Methods

Survey area: The survey was conducted within the Shaanxi Hanzhong Crested Ibis National Nature Reserve, which covers a total area of 375.49 km². The largest river in the reserve is the Han River, with 11 tributaries, and extensive paddy fields are present on both sides of the river valleys.

Survey time: The general bird survey was conducted from late 2024 to November 2025, lasting one year. The waterbird surveys have been carried out annually from 2020 to the end of 2025, each year between November and February.

Survey methods: Line transects, point counts, and supplementary interviews were primarily used. Based on the species composition and distribution characteristics of birds, as well as the habitat types within the reserve (forest, shrubland, river, farmland, and residential area), a total of 28 line transects (each 3.0 km in length) were established according to a sampling proportion. At least 4 transects were placed in each of the following habitat types: forest, shrubland, farmland, residential area, and wetland (Fig. S2). Transect surveys were conducted on foot at a speed of 1–2 km/h, recording the species name and number of birds observed.

Wintering waterbird surveys were conducted using point counts. 20 survey points were established along two major rivers within the reserve, the Xushui River and the Han River (covering approximately 40 km of river reaches) (Fig. S3). Birds around each point were recorded using a fixed-radius point count method (50–200 m). Observation time at each point ranged from 10 to 15 minutes.

Fig. S2 Distribution of bird survey transects in the Crested Ibis Nature Reserve. Yellow lines indicate survey transects, and blue lines indicate rivers

Fig. S3 Distribution of waterbird survey points in the Crested Ibis Nature Reserve. Green dots indicate survey points, and blue lines indicate rivers.

(2) Results and discussion

A total of 330 bird species were recorded in the Crested Ibis Nature Reserve, belonging to 18 orders, 66 families, and 196 genera. Among them, Passeriformes comprised 171 species (51.82%), representing 40 families and 94 genera, followed by Charadriiformes (30 species, 9.09%) and Anseriformes (29 species, 8.79%).

Since the initiation of the waterbird survey in 2020, new waterbird species have been recorded each year. By the end of 2025, a total of 15 new waterbird species had been added, of which 8 are nationally key protected species in China (Table S1).

Waterbirds, especially large species such as cranes, storks, and ibises, have strict requirements for habitat quality, depending on wetlands and riverine beaches with clean water, abundant food resources, and low human disturbance. Therefore, they are often considered important indicator species for assessing local ecological and environmental quality. The progressive annual increase in waterbird diversity sympatric with the Crested Ibis within the reserve confirms the effectiveness of habitat restoration measures (e.g., wetland restoration) for the ibis and reflects the integrity of the local ecosystem.

Table S1 Newly recorded nationally key protected waterbird species (eight species) in the Crested Ibis Reserve (2020–2025)

Order	Family	Species name	Scientific name (in Latin)
ANSERIFORMES	Anatidae	Greater White-fronted Goose	<i>Anser albifrons</i>
ANSERIFORMES	Anatidae	Mandarin Duck	<i>Aix galericulata</i>
ANSERIFORMES	Anatidae	Scaly-sided Merganser	<i>Mergus squamatus</i>
CICONIIFORMES	Ciconiidae	Black Stork	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>
PELECANIFORMES	Threskiornithidae	Eurasian Spoonbill	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>
PELECANIFORMES	Threskiornithidae	Glossy Ibis	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>
GRUIFORMES	Gruidae	Common Crane	<i>Grus grus</i>
CHARADRIIFORMES	Ibidorhynchidae	Ibisbill	<i>Ibidorhyncha struthersii</i>

4 Social conflicts

4.1 Socioeconomic benefits of Crested Ibis conservation

Liu et al. (2025) systematically expounded the status and implementation logic of socio-economic development (including organic agriculture) driven by Crested Ibis conservation (already cited in the main text). As that article was published in a Chinese journal, we provide here a brief introduction to the main data collection methods and relevant results to facilitate understanding.

(1) Methods

Data were obtained from two sources: a. Questionnaire surveys: Liu et al. conducted multiple household questionnaire surveys in Yang County between 2012 and 2024. The surveys covered basic household and individual information, household resource endowments, production and operation status, household income, assets and social relationships, participation in organic agriculture, and farmers' perceptions, attitudes, behaviors, and needs regarding biodiversity resources, ecosystem service values, the impact of protected area establishment on their production and daily life, and biodiversity conservation and related policies. b. Local data collection: Through a review of published materials and collection of local statistical data, they analyzed economic development changes in Yang County. During field visits, participatory interviews were conducted with the agricultural authorities of Yang County, township governments, and organic production enterprises, and relevant documents were collected. These included data and materials reflecting the natural, economic, and social conditions of the study area as well as the development of the organic industry, such as the Yang County national economic and social development statistical bulletin, Yang County ecological environment protection plan, Yang County organic industry development plan, Yang County national ecological product supply base construction plan, and the list of organic certification enterprises in Yang County.

(2) Results and discussion

Survey results showed that by the end of 2022, Yang County had registered the "Crested Ibis" trademark across 6 categories encompassing over 80 products. The potential value of the regional brand "Crested Ibis Ecological Organic Products" was estimated at \$1.3 billion, placing it among the top 100 national agricultural regional brands. Furthermore, based on household survey data and interview results from 2024, more than 80% of farmers agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that "the good environment brought by the Crested Ibis Nature Reserve enables the development of organic agriculture," indicating that most rural residents recognize the importance and value of protecting the Crested Ibis.

Pathway to achieving coordinated development between Crested Ibis conservation and socio-economics: building a multi-stakeholder system involving government, farmers, and enterprises

In practice, the Yang County government has encouraged farmers to refrain from using fertilizers and pesticides in fields within the ibis's activity and foraging areas, and to restore natural wetlands, thereby creating a suitable habitat for the Crested Ibis. Years of strict ecological protection have resulted in a high-quality environment, providing favorable conditions and a strong foundation for developing eco-industries, increasing farmers' incomes, and promoting local economic development. Farmer participation is the direct driving force and ultimate foundation of Crested Ibis conservation and community development. Survey results indicated that more than 95% of farmers are willing or very willing to protect the Crested Ibis and other wildlife and to create a safe and secure living environment for them. In their daily production and life, they voluntarily reduce

the use of fertilizers and pesticides to protect ibis' habitat. Enterprises play a key role. Because farmers, limited by planting scale and capital, often find it difficult to obtain organic certification directly, their participation in organic agriculture requires cooperation with agricultural enterprises or cooperatives. According to the 2024 household survey data, more than 70% of farmers engaged in organic farming sell their crops through contracts with companies. Enterprises are involved in all stages of organic agriculture—production, processing, and marketing—providing solutions to achieve the dual goals of ibis conservation and economic development.

In summary, conservation actions for the Crested Ibis in Yang County have not only improved local environmental quality but also successfully transformed ecological advantages into economic value. This economic growth has further strengthened people's willingness to protect the ibis and fostered a favorable situation of harmonious coexistence between humans and the Crested Ibis.

For more on the practical logic of human–Crested Ibis harmonious coexistence, see Liu et al. (2025). Liu G, Lv J, Hou Y. From Conflict to Symbiosis: A Chinese case of harmonious coexistence between humans and nature in the Crested Ibis habitat. *Natural Protected Areas*, 2025. (Online) <https://link.cnki.net/urlid/33.1417.s.20250630.1500.002>.

4.2 Public attitude toward Crested Ibis conservation

A survey on the willingness of community residents to support Crested Ibis conservation was conducted between 2021 and 2022. The methods, analyses, and results were published in 2022 in the *Journal for Nature Conservation*. For details, see:

Ren Y, Ding C, Zhang Y, et al. Public attitudes and willingness to pay toward the conservation of Crested Ibis: Insights for management. *Journal for Nature Conservation*, 2022;66, 126118.